

Leveraging the Socio-Economic Status of Persons With Disabilities Through Employment

ANDREWS AMENYO

Abstract

Nearly every State in the world recognizes people with disabilities (PWD) as a substantial protected class. Despite the state's economic and social development, they continue to confront job discrimination and other problems on a global scale. This essay examines the difficulties that job seekers with disabilities encounter in a few states and locations around the world. The relevance, applicability, efficacy, and efficiency of the United Nations Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities, as well as other municipal statutes and supplemental legislation, have all been evaluated. The high unemployment rate among those with disabilities may have several causes or contributing variables, which have all been carefully considered. The challenges faced by people with disabilities in the developing world when compared to those in the developed world with comparable democratic institutions and systems of governance were examined through a critical comparative analysis of Ghana, a small developing country in West Africa, and the United States of America. There are solutions and suggestions to aid all stakeholders that address the considerable challenges that persons with disabilities confront in their employment, job retention, and pay, as well as their inclusion and successful participation in the global labor market.

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About Author (s)

Andrews Amenyo, Law School, University of International Business and Economics (UIBE), Beijing, China.

1.0 Introduction

A recent estimate places the percentage of people with disabilities in the world's population at 15% (PWD). However, just 30% of those who are of working age are employed. Anti-employment discrimination laws and other disability policies were adopted toward the end of the 20th and the beginning of the 21st centuries in an effort to alleviate the suffering of People with Disabilities worldwide. Disability employment, while not unusual in terms of the global employment issues, is a silent weapon for poverty and suffering regardless of the origin or race of the victims (WHO 2015). Due to overt bias and discrimination towards people with disabilities, disability employment is one area where job discrimination has shown its ugly face. Employment discrimination is a problem that affects people with disabilities more frequently and openly than it affects those without disabilities, but for the wrong reasons preconceptions, a lack of educational and career possibilities. There aren't enough hospitals and rehabilitation facilities for persons with impairments in most countries, especially the poorest ones. Particularly in wealthy or developed nations, opportunities and facilities for people with impairments are insufficient or unevenly distributed.

Discrimination against physically challenged people or those with disabilities is still a common occurrence, whether it be in or out of the workplace, or in the workplace itself, despite the fact that employment rates for people with disabilities are higher in developed countries than in developing countries. Physically disabled people have valiantly overcome barriers to occupy their rightful place in society and the workforce, but much more must be done to improve the lives of people with disabilities without the assistance of 21st century stakeholders like governments, civil society, disabled organizations, and in some cases employers associations. Risky or unhealthy working conditions increase the likelihood that employees will be exposed to occupational risks and have accidents that leave them incapacitated. Sometimes is ugly, uncomfortable, or disgusting if it is true.

The UN passed the Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities (CRPD) in 2006 as a response to the dehumanization, exclusion, and discrimination of PWDs. By mandating States Parties to establish an inclusive education system at all levels and throughout a person's lifetime, Article 24 of this treaty reiterates the right of PWDs.¹

2.0 Research Methods

2.1 Research Methodology

This article used secondary data from international organizations including the United Nations and its relevant institutions, the World Bank, the International Monetary Fund, national or domestic publications of particular regions and states around the world, disability groups, and more.

Reputable local and international newspapers and magazines were referenced in order to provide other perspectives and enhance the quality and reliability of the information and materials used to portray a realistic picture of the employment challenges that PWD face. Both quantitative and high-quality data have been employed to attain objectivity. Since individuals with disabilities represent a sizable protected category in our society, data has been carefully adjusted to further study objectives and offer crucial information about how to enhance the employment chances of this group. The research design has taken into account the viewpoints

¹ Article 24 of Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities CRPD , 2006.

and practical experiences of numerous significant state barriers in order to reflect the concerns and reality of individuals with disabilities.

2.2 Research Objectives

The study's objectives are to: Increase understanding of the predicament of those with disabilities and offer workable ways to ameliorate it;

- Increase the employment chances and employment prospects of PWDs by offering them various job training and education opportunities;
- Providing governments and civil society with the most up-to-date scientific information, along with a clear explanation of the significance of disability and a study of the reactions given;
- To make suggestions for national and international stakeholders based on this analysis.

2.3 Research Questions

Persons with disabilities face numerous hurdles in pursuit of employment, this paper will address critical questions as follows:

- What critical employment challenges PWD faced?
- Are the employment challenges differ in the developing states from developed states ?
- The impacts of employment challenges on PDW worldwide?
- Is Anti-employment discrimination laws adhered to by employers ?
- How best can these challenges be addressed ?

3.0 Employment challenges of PWD

3.1 Low education attainment

People with disabilities need the free, universal, and mandated education that many nations throughout the globe offer. Even though the information at hand reveals that PWD continue trail behind when it comes to access to education, the UN Conventions on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities (CRPD) enter into force had a favorable impact on PWD's prospects in the educational arena.

The majority of lucrative employment in the twenty-first century demand a standard education, or at the very least, the most basic academic credentials. So, for PWDs, finishing education is either a condition or increase the chances that they will be able to find quality employment. Both the perception of workplace discrimination and the significant wage gap between persons with disabilities and their fortunate opposite coworkers are directly tied to this. In all industries, employers take a candidate's education into account when recruiting for white color jobs to be precise. The World Report on Disability 2011, chapter 7,² which undertakes a critical examination of PWDs' educational attainment and level, contains the pertinent data that serves as the basis for this analysis.

Participants with disabilities in the World Health Survey are less likely than participants without disabilities to finish elementary or middle school, and they are also more likely to have completed fewer mean years of education. for each of the 51 nations that were examined. Compared to 61.3 percent of men without disabilities, only 50.6 percent of men with disabilities have completed elementary school. Just 41.7% of girls with disabilities completed primary school, as opposed to 52.9% of girls without disabilities. People with disabilities typically have a similar number of fewer years of education than people without disabilities (males: 5.96 versus 7.03 years respectively; females: 4.98 versus 6.26 years respectively). For

² *The World Report on Disability 2011, chapter 7.*

both sub-samples of low-income and high-income states, there are statistically significant differences in the rates at which students finish their education across all age groups.

It will take a lot of work to remove barriers, make the necessary accommodations, and give these children access to mainstream educational opportunities, even though all children with disabilities have a right to individual support and participation in general education systems.³ The education challenges PWD confront continue to prevent them from finding jobs, not with standing rules and other actions made by stakeholders. When choosing potential personnel, businesses adhere to tight screening requirements, they wish to choose people who are extremely qualified in order to boost production and increase their outputs.

In today's brutally competitive world, the majority of businesses must fight for existence, with turning a profit being one of their primary objectives. Even non-profit organizations stress quality, efficacy, and efficiency in their work, including government agencies, the UN, and its affiliates, as well as other institutions. In order to fill crucial roles, they must find applicants with advanced degrees and a ton of expertise, but data suggest that few PWD have been successful in doing so. Their academic achievements can be held largely responsible for PWDs' lack of proportionate involvement and representation in the labor market.⁴

3.2 Health Condition or Impact

By virtue of their medical conditions, people with disabilities may occasionally be constrained or limited, which has an impact on productivity. In order to lessen the consequences on productivity, both employers and coworkers frequently find it difficult to understand or cooperate with their unusual circumstances; instead, they seek to eliminate PWD. PWD attrition rates might be concerning in several industries, particularly the private sector. Many businesses are hesitant or afraid to hire PWD because they worry that the reliability and consistency of their production cannot be guaranteed, leading to drops in productivity. PWD health can also decline at times more quickly than that of their peers without disabilities. Some people contend that regardless of their physical capabilities or position, every employee gets sick or may even call in sick, hence accommodations or procedures should be put in place to handle such medical situations. Being aware of an possible or potential interruption in work operations cannot be traded for any consideration. The obstacle of PWD having less possibilities due to tenable or weak justifications continues. Here's an example of a common disability that affects both children and adults. The disorder that affects movement and coordination is called dyspepsia, commonly referred to as developmental co-ordination disorder (DCD). Research has demonstrated that it has a negative impact on productivity. Dyspraxia or apraxia is an illustration of a health issue that has a significant negative impact on a person's employment ability.

Although dyspraxia has no effect on IQ, it can make daily tasks more difficult and restrict a person's ability to meet specific job criteria. It can reduce the ability to coordinate, which is important for duties like driving a car, which is becoming more and more popular as a means of transit to work in many states today, or for jobs requiring balance and mobility. It is challenging to write or handle little things because of this disability. According to medical professionals, the symptoms of Dyspraxia can differ from person to person and can change over

³ under the United Nations Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities (CRPD).

⁴ Fulton, S.A., and E.J. Sabornie (1994). 'Evidence of employment inequality among females with disabilities'. *The Journal of Special Education*, 28(2): pp.149-65.

time. Because of this, it can be challenging for employers or supervisors to make accommodations for disabled employees so that their inability to complete tasks on time does not lead to productivity lapses. Even simple chores could become challenging, and functioning at work could be challenging, particularly in labor-intensive occupations. Dyspraxia issues could be summed up as follows:

- writing, typing, drawing, and grasping small objects;
- mobility, balance, and coordination;
- the ability to learn new material, use critical thinking, and retain it both at work and during leisure activities;
- daily life abilities include dressing up or making meals on schedule;
- social situations; controlling your emotions;
- and time management, planning, and personal organization.

Employers mostly, business organizations are profit-driven or at least to break-even in order to survive, honor their obligations, pay rents, salaries and other bills, as such cannot afford to hire or retain employees with certain disabilities that is likely to affect their output and to lower productivity. Dyspraxia disability employees on assembly lines will derail the progress of work and frustrate colleagues and supervisors, thus putting their operation plans and targets into jeopardy. Other medical conditions experienced by some disability members of the workforce can't be ascertained because, they are spontaneous, due these realities and fears, Persons With disabilities have to grapple with these unfortunate situations which obviously lead to their exclusion from the workforce in some cases.

3.3 PWD in the workplace

People with impairments have a range of challenges at employment. Many people with disabilities also encounter bias because of the attitudes of their employees. Some problems are based on their specific impairment, such as the difficulty of someone in a wheelchair to access goods that are out of arm's reach. In actuality, even during periods of low unemployment, PWD want to work but can't find a job find it difficult to even get employed at all. There are various irritants in the working environment for people with disability.

Disabilities of any kind, especially those that are obvious, continue to carry a stigma. There are numerous obstacles in the workplace that discriminate against people with impairments. Assuming that a disabled person needs your assistance because you don't trust them to complete their tasks on their own. The truth is that folks who live with disabilities are just as capable of finishing their tasks as those who do not. The impaired employee's and his or her coworkers' confidence is impacted by this false or unfounded perception. In contrast to physical and systemic impediments, removing attitudes leads frequently to unlawful discrimination that is difficult to stop using the law. Section "S" ⁵ addresses physical impediments in the workplace. The Act establishes basic standards that every structure, including office space, must adhere to. If you hire a disabled person, you should make every effort to provide them with a reasonable accommodation, yet in advanced nations let alone underdeveloped nations this is not always the case. Sometimes, these rules go well beyond what is required of small and medium-sized businesses that rent office space in towering buildings.

⁵ Section "S" of the National Buildings Regulations and Buildings Act of the United States.

3.4 Transportation accessibility

The majority of disabled individuals rely on public transportation, which can be difficult for them to use because they don't typically own automobiles and frequently can't drive on their own. Owning a car and being able to drive are prerequisites for mobility or movement in today's culture. Even though other cities or countries have more robust public transportation systems, PWD accessibility is frequently a challenge in the world of public transportation.⁶ The very nature of transportation infrastructure restricts movement and entry to many public places. Lack of amenities and transportation choices prevents many PWD from entering the workforce; many won't even bother to look for work since they know they can't commute to places of employment. In Beijing and other cities across the world, disabled individuals commonly experience frustration when attempting to enter some downtown buildings or subways. The majority of developing countries' insufficient road networks.

3.5 Examining Employers' Concerns

Unintentional prejudices towards people with disabilities are all too common among employers. They support a diversified workplace and see themselves as objective. They think about how accessible their facility and office are and what further adjustments could be needed. Will they need more expensive, up-to-date desks with bigger openings? Do you need new shelves or any other specialized equipment? How much more would it cost to employ someone with a disability? Fundamentally, it is a fear of the unknown.

Experiments have been carried out where positions that can be occupied out just as well by a person with a disability, such as bookkeeper or accountant, were advertised. People who disclosed their disability in their cover letters got a lot less answers than people who didn't. The labor market in general does not accommodate disabilities, though, this situation has seen much improvement in recent years. Many redundancies or redeployment continue to have telling impacts on the labor front even in richer states and the world over. According to a disability employment advocate recorded by the South China Morning Post, bosses and colleagues indirectly push PWD from the workplace. This no news at all, considering the high unemployment rate experience by PWD the world over. Lay-offs or redundancies characterize the labor market due to the ever-changing world spearheaded by technology. PWD are the first to be hit by redundancies according to surveys, by employers and fellow employees without disabilities as documented by many researches finding across the globe. Most employers surveyed hold the view that PWD do not same competencies and capabilities as their counterparts without disabilities. PWD come first where employers consider downsizing their workforce, mere perceptions social stigma have made employers simply uncomfortable with disable workers.

Employers present the true challenge. Many firms are still apprehensive about hiring disabled" people because they fear that they can cause issues at work. An advocate for persons with disabilities finding work remarked. Furthermore, it is predicted that this kind of visit will be very expensive because the business is currently undergoing renovations to make it more accessible for those with disabilities. Every sector experiences workplace alterations on a regular basis, including the replacement of capital furnishings like furniture. Unfortunately, some companies appear to be ignorant of this demand and put the burden on employees with impairments. To guarantee that people with disabilities can work in environments that uphold freedom, equity security, and human dignity, there is either insufficient legislation or unenforced laws. Employers are more aware than

⁶ Only 25% of public places globally are accessible to persons with all forms of disability, according to a survey carried in the World Disability Report, 2011.

ever of the laws and rights that pertain to people with disabilities, even though they are not naive. As a result, they may take measures to avoid breaking the law, which is detrimental to the disabled employees. As a result, bringing a lawsuit against an employer over a particular decision may be very challenging. PWD are at a disadvantage on the job market for a variety of reasons, as the majority of companies struggle to stay afloat in this cutthroat, profit-driven business environment. PWD are disadvantaged in the labor market for many reasons as most businesses try to keep their heads above water in this competitive profit-oriented business world.⁷

3.6 Discrimination and prejudice

PWD are frequently not taken into account when hiring. Anywhere in the world, perception, fear, myth, and prejudice still make it difficult to understand and accept disability in the job. There are numerous myths out there, two of which are that people with impairments cannot work and that providing for them at work will be expensive.

Disabled people are significantly more vulnerable to prejudice and other forms of discrimination at employment as a result of disability-related stereotypes. There is no getting past the fact that there is blatant prejudice against disabled persons in almost every area of endeavor. According to polls, the majority of people would choose to purchase food or locally produced snacks from an able-bodied person if given the choice between the two. Employees with disabilities are occasionally made fun of and referred to as "eye-saws" rather than "troopers" for their organizations. "Disabled people are being forced out of the workforce by bosses and coworkers who do not comprehend their requirements." the social worker.⁸

Even though they are only views that have no impact on productivity, they impede PWD from finding mainstream work, especially in certain cultures or states in the developing world where disability is viewed as a curse. Ironically, there are times when businesses unintentionally discriminate against those who have disabilities. They see themselves as impartial and want to work in a diverse environment.

Making decisions about a person's employment based on their handicap is prohibited by anti-discrimination laws,⁹ While such clauses are already established in the constitutions of Ghana and Brazil, anti-discrimination clauses for people with disabilities have recently been added to general legislation in Germany and South Africa.

3.7 Socio-economic Factors

Though quantitative research on the socioeconomic status of PWD have shown increment in the economic well-being as compared to the last century. PWD with incomes, assets and overall financial standing ranks the lowest among protected groups in our society. They receive lower income and live-in poverty more than other marginalized groups in today's world. This situation makes them unattractive to employers to hire. Most of them do not drive or live downtown to be closer to business hubs or districts where most companies are located. Their residence locations alone disqualify from getting job interview offers, since most PWD can only afford cheaper rent which can only be found in the suburbs and other remote areas. Employers foresee huge and insurmountable commuting challenges on their part to and for work should

⁷ Gillian Marescia, an associate in Drake Recruitment's handicap branch. Disability employment is still a young field, according to Business Day South Africa on October 14, 2003.

⁸ Disabled people are being forced out of the workforce by bosses and coworkers who do not comprehend their requirements." the social worker. 5 July 2006, South China Morning Post.

⁹ The case in Australia (1992), Canada (1986, 1995), New Zealand (1993), and the United States (1990).

they hire them. it is imperative that a disable person with no private car and lives in the suburb won't be hired at the expense of job competitor who lives downtown and drives to the job interview. Poor economic status of PWD doesn't make much sense, especially with many anti-employment legislations but critical decision-making factors for employers. The prospective employers consider punctuality and flexibility in movement to meet tasks expectations or impromptu assignments and unplanned overtime which characterized today's working life. Employees often receive urgent tasks and calls to do undertake certain unscheduled tasks. Many Human Resource practitioners can attest to this. When these and many factors play to the disadvantage of PWD, one answer to the question why the unemployment rates of PWD are higher across the globe? They are unable to attend interviews and dress professionally enough to leave a favorable impression because of their poor finances.

Descriptive data indicate that people with disabilities have disadvantages in educational achievement and employment outcomes, similar to those in industrialized countries. The social security system for people with disabilities needs improvement. The system's financial resources, which primarily come from government contributions, are rather meager. For poverty status as determined by asset ownership, housing situation, income, and consumption expenditures, the evidence is weaker.

3.8 Lack of Employment Services

To improve the social and economic inclusion of people with disabilities by better educating the public about their rights and employment opportunities, media representatives should receive training. This training should include initiatives created specifically to improve these people's employ ability and employment. Cases on Promoting Employment for People with Disabilities" in order to give employers advice and resources for including and supporting the disabled as well as to inspire the disabled to start their own businesses. The gap between those with disabilities and others in terms of living conditions is growing. Poverty remains a significant impediment to the growth of the disabled population. Lack of social protection, employment opportunities, education, and vocational training for those with disabilities.

3.9 The Enforce ability of Laws

"Reasonable accommodations" are changes made to the workplace and job to make it easier for people with disabilities to work in the formal sector, provided that doing so does not impose an unreasonable burden on others. Anti-discrimination laws forbid making decisions about a person's employment based on their disability.

Certain legislative tools need to be enhanced after receiving more attention. "Getting Equal Employment Opportunities for People with Disabilities through Legislation" is a seminar offered by the ILO. Stakeholder awareness of laws and policies pertaining to disabilities, particularly those that deal with consultation, implementation, and enforcement, has not increased.

Appropriate policies and supportive measures must be created to guarantee that people with mental illness and/or intellectual disability have equitable employment opportunities. Training materials will be developed to combat discrimination based on a variety of factors, including race or ethnicity, color, sex, sexual orientation, religion, social origin, impairments, and infectious diseases, among others.

As in other developing nations, PWDs in Ghana still run into prejudice when trying to access opportunities for employment and education.¹⁰ According to Hoogeveen, Uganda's employment rates for people with disabilities were lower than those for people without disabilities (2005). The results of the ILO instrument on entrepreneurial development¹¹ show that PWDs have lower employment rates.¹²

4.0 Global overview & Analysis

4.1 The Global Picture

In light of the numerous rules that are in place on an international and domestic level, the situation for PWD employment around the world is bleak and depressing. Overall PWD employment figures are still much too low to be considered acceptable. PWD unemployment rates average from 50 to 70 percent in industrialized states, but they are between 80 and 90 percent in developing nations.

Neither industrialized nor developing countries have employment rates for people with disabilities that are higher than 30%, despite estimates that there are more than a billion of them worldwide. This problem affects PWD as well as other societal problems, the global economy, and GDP.

According to household surveys, damaged parent families in a particular town performed worse than any other protected group. Because of their extreme poverty, these families are unable to even meet the rising cost of their children's education, let alone meet their other essential needs. If PWD are kept out of the mainstream labor market, the numerous initiatives against poverty put forth by the United Nations, the World Bank, the International Monetary Fund, and other organizations will be ineffective. According to estimates, if the employment rate for people with disabilities increased by more than 50% globally, the world economy might expand by about 0.5 percentage points. As giving lip service to their needs dominates the responses or action plan, reducing PWD unemployment to an appreciable level is a difficult task, if not "mission impossible." Even though the United Nations Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities (UNCRPD) was intended to serve as a legal safeguard and inspire new legislation to better PWD conditions, the majority of disabled people continue to be jobless and live-in squalor and extreme poverty.

4.2 Asia and the Pacific

This region is the most populous region of the world and most of the world's fastest growing economies are located in Asia, but unfortunately, disability employment equally suffers. The few disable employees who work at mainstream jobs have experience discrimination, lost of employment and other unfavorable labor outcome over the years.

238 million of the world's more than 370 million disabled persons are of working age. In "Disability Issues in the Employment and Social Protection,"¹³

In India, 94 percent of people with mental retardation and 74% of people with physical disability are unemployed. All parties are extremely concerned about the startlingly high

¹⁰ *Between 1998 and 2006, PWDs' employment and participation in the labor force in South Africa fell, claims Mitra. (2008).*

¹¹ *see Article 2 of the CRPD.*

¹² *The 2008 publications The CDPF Facts and Progress on Disability in China and The Second National Sampling Survey on Disability.*

¹³ *ILO Bangkok, 2002, Debra A. Perry claims that their unemployment rate is twice as high as the general population's and frequently exceeds 80% or higher.*

percentage of disabled individuals who are unemployed in a nation with more than a billion inhabitants. The unemployment rate for people with disabilities in the Republic of Korea is approximately 30%, which is five or six times higher than the national average. Vietnam Of the 5.1 million people with impairments, about 69 percent are of working age (16 to 55-60). Only 30% of them have steady jobs that provide their families with money.

Asia Regional Report of the International Disability Rights Monitor's 2005 Asia-Pacific China An excerpt from "Social Worker" claims that "Bosses and employees who do not understand their requirements are driving disabled persons out of the workforce".¹⁴ The law was ratified on August 30, 2007, by the Standing Committee of the Tenth National People's Congress, and it became effective on January 1, 2008.

4.3 The European Union

There are about 40 million PWD, and in 1998, between 43 and 54 percent of them were of working age. Two to three times as many people with impairments are unemployed as the general population. Although it has the most developed economies, is socially more sophisticated, and has strong legislation to promote the socioeconomic welfare of PWD, the European Union nevertheless has a high unemployment rate relative to those without disabilities. Even in the face of laws and other measures that have been established over the years, the unemployment hoodoos of this protected class are worrying.

For instance, the National Statistical Service's 2002 survey on people with health difficulties or disabilities and the International Disability Rights Monitor's Regional Report on Europe from 2007 both show that the unemployment rate for people with disabilities in Greece is 84 percent.

The status of nations like Greece in Western Europe, probably the richest part of the world or the region with the biggest concentration of developed or wealthy nations on the planet, makes this scenario frightening. Employment of people with disabilities is a crucial problem because it directly affects the household's standard of life. The consequences are severe if a larger proportion of a group of people in the society lack job or other means of supporting themselves and their families. No wonder Greece was plundering in economic turmoil in 2012, roughly 10 years after the 2002 survey; this shows how unemployment can serve as a key indicator, though this can be disputed, and it's synonymous throughout the developing world as PWD unemployment continues to be drag many economies into serious economic predicament. Beyond marginalization and exclusion from chances offered by the mainstream, disability unemployment exists. In Europe as well as other regions of the world, there are other additional factors that contribute to disability unemployment.

For instance, in **Austria**, there were around 91,000 registered people with impairments in 2005, with about 23,000 of them working and another 31,000 either economically inactive or primarily unemployed. Employment in the **UK**:¹⁵ The Labor Force Survey shows that the labor force participation rate for people with disabilities is still significantly lower than it is for people without impairments, notwithstanding an uptick since 2002. Compared to 76.4 percent of adults without disabilities, only 46.3% of working-age people with disabilities were

¹⁴ *South China Morning Post*, 5 July 2006.

¹⁵ Bell D, Heitmueller A. *The Disability Discrimination Act in the UK: helping or hindering employment among the disabled?* *Journal of Health Economics*, 2009,28: pp.465-480. doi:10.1016/j.jhealeco.2008.10.006 PMID:19091434 • 254.

employed in 2012. Therefore, the difference between individuals with disabilities and those without is 30.1 percentage points, or more than 2 million people. Over the past 14 years, the differential has shrunk by 10 percentage points, and despite the state of the economy, it has remained stable over the last two years.

According to the Federal Service of Labor and Employment, 70% of Russians with disabilities are unemployed. One-fifth of the working-age population, or 6.8 million of the 10 million disabled people in the UK are employed, regardless of their level of education, those with disabilities and those who experience ongoing health issues have lower employment rates than the general population. People with impairments are more likely to be unemployed than other citizens by a factor of three, despite the fact that they still desire to work at all levels of ability.

4.4 Latin America and the Caribbean

Due to the region's extremely unpredictable labor markets and weak economies, Latin America has one of the lowest employment rates worldwide for people with disabilities. Between 80 and 90 percent of people with impairments are unemployed or not working. According to the most recent World Bank data, the majority of people with work make little to no money. Although it is a consequence of the amount of poverty and employment discrimination in the Latin American area, disability unemployment has other contributing factors. Policymakers and others were unable to fight for or concentrate on the needs of the disabled, the majority of whom are victims of their acts due to the unstable political climate and authoritarian administrations with dictatorial tendencies. Disabilities are a result of avoidable accidents and pointless conflicts. The employment outcome of PWDs who are working age continues to be significantly impacted by the lack of educational accommodations and possibilities in the majority of countries.

According to reports, Argentina, one of the most populated nations in the world with infrastructure that is superior to that of half the states in the region, has a rate of unemployment for people with disabilities that is close to 91 percent. Compared to 51.6% of the general population, just 25.1% of Chile's disabled population is employed in any form. Persons with disabilities have a much lower employment rate than people without impairments, despite Chile having one of the most vibrant economies in the region. Despite several pro-disability work laws adopting disability rights programs and methods, there is still disabled job discrimination, or the systematic exclusion of individuals with disabilities from mainstream employment possibilities. According to disability organizations, Costa Rica's unemployment rate is approximately 65 percent. In Honduras, a household survey conducted in 2002 by the National Institute of Statistics found that just 49% of disabled people who are of working age are employed.

4.5 The United States of America

The employment of PWD is comparably lower than that of individuals without impairments, despite recent evidence showing improvement. Because of erroneous assumptions, many companies misunderstand the Americans with Impairments Act and are hesitant to recruit people with disabilities.

The ADA related difficulties have been explained in detail. The use of everyday language and busting of myths regarding this frequently underutilized source of highly competent workers. As a result, a lot of current or prospective employers are reluctant to hire PWD. The employment population ratio for people with disabilities rose from 18.7% in 2017 to 19.1% in 2018. In 2018, the percentage of people without a disability increased to 65.9 percent.

Nevertheless, across all age groups, those with disabilities had a much lower likelihood of being employed than those without disabilities.

PWDs are less likely than non-disabled people to have a bachelor's degree or above. More education was consistently associated with a greater likelihood of getting employment for both categories. The employment rates of people with disabilities were much lower than those of people without impairments in 2018 across all educational levels. Across all age groups, the employment-population ratios for those with impairments were much lower than those for those without impairments.

At all educational levels, those with disabilities experience higher unemployment rates than those without disabilities. In contrast to those without impairments, who made up only 17 percent of the workforce in 2018, people with disabilities made up 31% of it. Compared to non-disabled employees, employees with disabilities were more likely to work as independent contractors.

According to the Americans with Disabilities Act (ADA) of 1990,¹⁶ it is unlawful to discriminate against qualified individuals with disabilities in job applications, hiring, firing, promotions, compensation, job training, and other conditions, terms, and privileges. All organizations, including unions, municipal, state, and private governments, as well as employment agencies, are prohibited from doing this.¹⁷

The ADA Amendments Act of 2008 (ADAAA),¹⁸ The ADAAA criticizes two Supreme Court decisions that decreased protection for many disabled people that Congress had intended to provide,¹⁹ The ADAAA broadens protection and coverage in a number of different ways.²⁰ The EEOC modifies its rules in 2011 to implement the ADA's employment restrictions. The amended regulations take into account how the term "disability" was intended to be used by Congress when the ADAAA modified the meaning of the term.

According to a 2004 poll, only 35% of working-age adults with disabilities are employed, compared to 78% of the general population. When asked why they couldn't work, two-thirds of respondents with impairments who were unemployed said they wished they could. The employment rate for people with a four-year degree is 89.9 percent for both men and women. The employment rate for college graduates with impairments is 50.6 percent.

4.6 Ghana

All children should have equitable access to high-quality education, according to the Ghana Education Strategy strategy for 2003.²¹ The goal of the policy was to ensure that kids with less severe special needs or disabilities attended segregated special schools or special units that were integrated into regular classrooms, while kids with severe and profound disabilities went

¹⁶ Acemoglu D, Angrist J. *Consequences of employment protection? The case of the Americans with Disabilities Act. The Journal of Political Economy*, 2001,109: pp.915-957. doi:10.1086/322836.

¹⁸ President George W. Bush signed into law in September, becomes effective on January 1, 2009.

¹⁹ *Toyota Motor Manufacturing, Kentucky, Inc. v. Williams, US 184, and Sutton v. United Airlines, Inc., US 471 (1999).*

²⁰ Mitra S. *Temporary and partial disability programs in nine countries: what can the United States learn from other countries? Journal of Disability Policy Studies*, 2009,20: pp.14-27.

²¹ Avoke, M. (2001). 'Some historical perspectives in the development of Special Education in Ghana'. *European Journal of Special Needs*, 16: pp.29-40.

to special schools that were separate from regular classrooms (MoE 2013). According to Appiagyei (2006) and Kassah (2008),²² many disabled Ghanaian face a lack of economic possibilities in addition to living in poverty, being uneducated, obtaining inadequate medical care, and having trouble feeding themselves. This is accurate despite the fact that the law is in force. In their detailed examination of fifteen carefully chosen developing nations, including Ghana, Mitra, Posarac, and Vick (2013) discovered a strong link between disability and worse multidimensional poverty, less educational attainment, lower job rates, and higher medical costs.²³ Enrollment figures may have been significantly impacted by the high rates of stigmatization, humiliation, and social exclusion that children with disabilities encounter in the classroom.

4.7 Benefits PWD Staff

Companies can gain from the benefits that people with impairments have. According to research, some of them include being dependable and loyal, working hard, and having low absenteeism rates. The diversification of work environments that resulted from hiring people with impairments created a climate at work that was generally favorable. The organization benefits greatly from having personnel that is truly diversified and has a variety of abilities. The majority of businesses desire diversity and devoted workers who add value to their organizations.

That persons with impairments are more than capable has been recognized by many businesses. PWD turn to be more reliable, task oriented and stable employees, they work meticulous and contribute positively to the success of the organization as documented in many findings.

4.8 Attributes of Employees With Disabilities

Persons With Disabilities have proven beyond doubts that they are formidable and competent workers across industries all the world. Contrary to perceptions and unfounded employers concerns that PWD have negative outcomes on worker productivity, PWD have demystified the erroneous and baseless allegations that their inclusion in the employee roll call spells doom for the organization an such pose threat to higher productivity. PWD have succeeded in almost every field of endeavor whether as employees or self-employed. They have proven that handicapped is neither excuse or inability to work and succeed if the right conditions are present. Already employed people with disabilities have demonstrated that they are extremely dependable, take fewer sick days than the general population, and have good job retention rates (staying at their jobs).

Additionally, the safety records of those with disabilities are better. They experience fewer workplace accidents, maybe as a result of their awareness of their own limitations and the risks they can and cannot take. Everyone has both strengths and shortcomings; nobody is completely able or wholly incapacitated. An inebriated accountant is still an accountant. He might be the best accountant he's ever seen, but an employer who overlooks him due to his impairment might be doing him a disservice.

²² Kassah, A.K. (2008). *Begging as work: A study of people with mobility difficulties in Accra, Ghana*. *Disability & Society*, 23(2): 163–70.

²³ According to statistics, just 6% of Ghana's 679,000–804,000 disabled children attend any kind of educational program (GES 2004).

4.9 Diversity Includes PWD

Diversity which many employers tout themselves of is not just about workers from different cultural backgrounds or races or unisex or balanced gender representation in the workforce. The inclusion of employees with disabilities is a further ingredient to consider, since they contribute their knowledge and experience to the workplace, really diversifying it.

Diversity is the total inclusion of all people with the ability to work and achieve organizational goals. The inclusion and participation. The inclusion of staff with disability can serve as inspiration to colleague without disabilities as well as encourage prospective employees with disabilities which goes a long way to leverage the socioeconomic status of the individual, the company and the society at large, as it portrays the society and state progressive and civil ideals.

A company that employs persons with disabilities gains the following additional advantages: increasing variety Employers frequently refer to individuals of various nationalities and ethnicities when they talk about seeking a varied workforce; they hardly ever consider how hiring someone with a disability can increase diversity. However, doing so can provide everyone in the company's perspectives more depth. A person with a disability has had a unique set of experiences throughout their life that others have not. Observing the contributions of someone who has overcome major challenges might increase others' drive and understanding.

Numerous federal and state programs, such as the Work Opportunity Tax Credit, offer cash to assist with hiring, training, and integrating new recruits into the workforce, as well as compensation for any adjustments made for a disability (WOTC), such as: Credit with Restricted Access and Tax deduction for removing barriers.

Most individuals with disabilities want to live honorable and valuable lives, just like everyone else. Employment offers social contact opportunities in addition to financial help. This is vital for those who have impairments in particular. Everyone, not just a small minority, should invest in systems and facilities for those who have impairments. Many companies have found that by hiring handicapped individuals, they are better equipped to understand and serve their disability clients. Different work groups produce better solutions to business issues. The flexibility, brand recognition, and market share of companies who offer services that can be customized to meet the various demands of people with disabilities are all improved.

5.0 Global Analysis of Employment of PWD

5.1 Developed Countries

PWD are more likely to live in poverty and have worse job and other labor market outcomes than those without disabilities. Even in developed countries, the problem of unemployment due to disabilities persists. In all but three of the upper-middle and high-income nations the OECD analyzed in 2009, working-age persons with disabilities experience poverty at a higher rate than working-age people without disabilities. In Australia, Ireland, and the Republic of Korea, the likelihood of relative poverty was more than twice as high for working-age non-disabled people. The lowest relative risk of poverty, which was just marginally higher than that of non-disabled people, was seen in Iceland, Mexico, and the Netherlands. People with disabilities who are working age have a double the likelihood of being unemployed, it is recognized. They are more likely to work part-time when they are employed. Additionally, they made very little money unless they had advanced degrees. Descriptive statistics show that people with disabilities face obstacles to achieving academic success and employment that are

on par with those in developed nations. For poverty status as determined by asset ownership, housing situation, income, and consumption expenditures, the evidence is weaker.

The poverty rates among households with disabled family members have been calculated in several research while taking into consideration the greater cost of living. Depending on the assumptions made using a 60 percent median income criterion, a study from the United Kingdom found that the poverty rate among households with disabled individuals was 20 to 44 percent higher in the late 1990s.²⁴

5.2 Developing Countries

Though it is still in its infancy, quantitative research on the socioeconomic circumstances of people with disabilities in developing countries has recently developed. According to the World Disability Report, the vast majority of studies indicate that people with disabilities perform badly in school and have lower employment rates than those without impairments. how many people are unemployed the shockingly high number of disabled people plus the shockingly high unemployment rate in the world's poorest countries are a surefire recipe for economic turmoil. For obvious reasons, such as a lack of professional opportunities, educational requirements, and other factors, PWD in the developing world suffer more than their counterparts in the industrialized world to find employment.

While the employment rate for those of working age who are not disabled is at least over 50%, it does not only apply to PWD because the employment rate for those who are disabled is typically less than 20% in developing countries. It is evident from comparing the unemployment statistics of the developed and developing worlds that PWD in the developed world have better job results than those in the developing because PWD are given special care and policy in their respective cultures. Regarding acceptance and accommodations, there are significant differences between the two professional settings and attitudes toward PWD. Better job outcomes undoubtedly result from more tolerant attitudes and empathy for the plight of employees or coworkers with disabilities in more developed nations.

In some impoverished or small-town settings, disability can occasionally be viewed as a curse, which is bad for retention and employment prospects. families with handicapped relatives spend more on health care than households without, according to a World Health Survey analysis of data from 15 developing countries (for 51 World Health Survey countries in the Disability World Report). Instead, compared to those without impairments, people with disabilities have significantly fewer job options and pay for the same task. According to a December 5, 2005 article in The Washington Times, people with impairments still encounter obstacles in the workplace. Disability Issues in Work and Social Protection in Thailand was written in 2002 by Debra A. Perry of the ILO Latin America and the Caribbean. Brazil's "Disability and Inclusive Development" 2004 report found that people there were willing to labor A EUROPS research, World Bank, 2004. Developing inclusive policies for individuals with disabilities in Latin America and the Caribbean Development and Disability Inclusion in Latin America and the Caribbean There are still not enough disabled people working, according to the 2006 International Disability Rights Monitor, Regional Report of the Americas, 2004, published by the European Foundation for the Improvement of Living and Working Conditions. July 5, 2006 Malaysian Morning Post We are fired from our jobs because we lack comprehension.

²⁴ Road accident indicator from the OECD ((Accessed on 04 July 2019).Doi: 10.1787/2fe1b899-en.

5.3 Availability of Jobs

The developed world boasts of better employment outcomes and chances, the overall employment landscape in developed states is stable and promising. Job creation is on the increase, opening up employment chances for both persons with and without disabilities. The availability of labor coupled with better educational infrastructure and quality education accessible to PWD facilitate their inclusion and participation in the job market with much ease. Industry and employers are more open to all marginalized or protected classes in our society. PWD as a protected class benefit more in this environment as employers not only adhere to disability legislations but also sympathetic to the plight of disables in the workplace. The inclusion of PWD in the labor force in the developed world is seen as both legal and moral obligations on the part of the employers and other citizens. Citizens in the developed world patronize the products or services of PWD without discrimination or reservation about their physical conditions. Self-employed disables and their businesses do not encounter much discrimination and rejection as compared to their counterparts in the developing sates according World Disability Reports.²⁵

• The Caribbean and Latin America

Between 80 and 90 percent of people with impairments are unemployed or not working. Most people who work make little or no money from their jobs.

• Latin America

The unemployment rate for those with impairments is thought to be close to 91 percent.

• In Canada

More than five times greater than the rate of 5% for those without disabilities, the unemployment rate for those with disabilities is 26 percent. Regional Report of the Americas, International Disability Rights Monitor, 2004.

• Greek

According to the National Statistical Service's Survey on People with Health Problems or Disability, 84 percent of people with disabilities are unemployed (second semester of 2002).

• India

94 percent of people with mental impairment and 74% of people with physical disability are unemployed.²⁶

• Mexican

Nationwide statistics show that 22.6 percent of workers with disabilities earn less than the minimum wage, while 14.6% of them do not receive any compensation at all.

• New Zealand

In New Zealand, one in five people are disabled.

6.0 Solutions & Suggestions

6.1 Suggested Solutions for Education

The central and local governments should take concrete steps to integrate or include PWD in main stream education. The work catastrophes or mishaps are mostly attributable to PWDs' lack of educational options. According to existing data and previous research, people with disabilities globally perform substantially worse than people without disabilities. In low-income or developing nations worldwide, the situation is significantly worse. To improve their

²⁵ *Disability and Inclusive Development Report for Latin America and the Caribbean, World Bank, 2004.*

²⁶ *International Disability Rights Monitor's 2005 Asia Regional Report.*

prospects of finding employment, governments and other stakeholders should expand the engagement and inclusion of PWD in early childhood educational institutions and tertiary and professional credentials. All students with disabilities should have action plans and pathways that are realistic and feasible to implement. Experts, educators, and caregivers should collaborate to provide everyone PWD with accessible and high-quality education, regardless of where they live or how well off, they are.

For the following reasons, including disabled children and adults in school has significant implications and advantages for society.

Education improves and adds value to the creation of human capital and is a crucial factor in determining one's own welfare. The lack of employment prospects for PWD leads to severe social and economic costs as a result of their exclusion from educational opportunities. The Millennium Educational Development Goal of universal primary school completion cannot be met without the involvement of children or PWD. The CRPD has a major provision requiring Contracting States to uphold their responsibilities under Article 24.

6.2 Applicability of Conventions & Laws

Many promulgation, laws, legislation and constitutional instruments have been postulated in recent decades in favor of PWD. These international conventions and domestic legislation have benefited PWD in many ways, through education, employment, medicare and social welfare benefits, but there is a long way to go, a lot more needed to be done in terms law regulatory framework in many jurisdictions worldwide. The enforce ability and application of these laws must be intensified to cover all PWD irrespective of the nature of their disability and other considerations. Often times, these measures are poorly administered and mismanaged dues to incompetency and corruptive nature of relevant agencies and departments, especially in developing countries. Also, there are infrastructural deficit or lack of resources in poorer countries. Resource mobilization and acquisition is central to alleviating the plight of PWD. The economic cost of educating disables is comparatively lower than putting them on meager benefits for their lifetime. Therefore, both Persons With Disability and the society equally benefit a lot if the former is gainfully employed. The regulations in many jurisdictions have loopholes that many employers and the larger society exploit to the disadvantage of these vulnerable members of the society. If PWD have access to quality education and gain employment skills, they will be able contribute positively to socio-economic development of their respective states there contributing to world economic growth. The strengthening of regulations, proper and diligent applications and sanctioning offenders whose actions affect the fortune and wellness of Persons With Disabilities must be done urgently.

6.3 Accidents

Disability in general can be reduced drastically throughout the world. This seems contentious but considering that disability increases as people growth , take the United States, a well developed country in almost every aspect . Disability with persons aged five and below stands at at 1%. So it's obvious that disability is being "nursed , or allowed to grow through ineffective or unguided human actions. Occupational accidents remain one key area where disability emanates from. Workplace accidents are prevalent and continues to render able bodied disables throughout the world. Collapse of mines alone account for a great proportion of PWD. Other workplace hazards continue to render people disables on daily bass if not hourly basis. Workplace safety standards and other safety measures should be adopted strictly. Motor traffic accidents or accidents in the transport industry also contribute largely to making people disables.

Every year, 1.35 million people lose their lives in traffic accidents. An additional 20 to 50 million people experience non-fatal injuries, and many of them develop impairments over time. Low- and middle-income nations, which also house about 60% of the world's autos, account for 93% of all traffic deaths.²⁷

6.4 Family & Society Responsibility

Families or parents should reduce the likelihood of creating PWD in many ways. Even before becoming pregnant, women who aspire to bear children in the future should desist from excessive alcoholism, drug usage, avoid smoking and other activities that are harmful to the future child. Research have shown that many disabilities can be avoided.

Prenatal care for the unborn child as soon as pregnancy is detected and regular check until the child is delivered as well as post-natal care when the child is delivered. Safety measures at home and during the upbringing of children is crucial in reducing disability. If parents adopt safety standards at home, it will reduce home accidents greatly.

There are no estimates of the specific injury-related causes of disability on a global or regional scale. However, estimates from some nations indicate that violence and injury related disabilities could account for up to 25% of all disabilities. Communities should improve their beliefs and perceptions and include PWD in their activities and program, involve their participation and inclusion in social undertakings. Public places should be disable friendly, create access to all public places such as recreational centers, schools, hospitals, public transportation among others. Avoid reprehensible actions such as violence and bullying of PWD.

6.5 Government Initiatives

Governments, both central and local governments should embark on strategic initiatives for job creation with special quota for PWD. More PWD should be employed in government departments and state-owned enterprises. It is proven that PWD can do almost every job if the conditions are right, so more civil service jobs should be allocated for qualified persons with disabilities. Government departments should procure items from disabilities or pro disabilities enterprises or affiliated companies. Government should come out with blueprint initiatives that aimed at creating and sustaining employment opportunities for PWD.

Disability should be taken into consideration in development assistance programs by using the twin-track model (mainstreaming and targeted). To set objectives for your initiatives, learn from your mistakes, and stop wasting time and resources, exchange information and coordinate your activities. States' economies would expand if there was a higher employment rate for people with impairments.

Stakeholder involvement is necessary for the creation of instruments for acquiring data to assess disability as well as other planning processes for gathering, tabulating, and disseminating disability data. Governmental organizations, data suppliers, individuals with disabilities, non-governmental organizations, and researchers are a few of the parties involved in the development and application of disability policy. People with impairments should

²⁷ *Report from the World Health Organization, 2018.*

actively engage in and be considered in the producer/user conversation.²⁸ Raising Our Ambitions: Disability, Skills, and Work, Disability Rights Commission, June 2007.

6.6 PWD Personal Effort

People with disabilities should make every effort to educate themselves and support one another by providing opportunities and information. They should actively participate in projects and training courses designed to improve their situation. They should put in more effort, demonstrate why they belong in the labor force, and excel at their jobs and tasks by meeting or exceeding their obligations.

PWD should take part in international, national, and local forums to establish change priorities, shape policy, and reshape service delivery. To improve their lot, they should be included in practically all programs, including research and other investigative ones. At all times, they should put their own education ahead of that of their kids and other dependants. They should adopt positive attitudes and perspectives and exhibit self-belief, boldness, confidence, and conviction to alter their current situation.

7.0 Conclusion

Governments and human rights organizations have stepped up their efforts to increase work prospects for individuals with disabilities globally over the last three to four decades. In the interim, more work is needed to support those programs. If job gaps between able-bodied and impaired people are to be closed, a coordinated effort must be made. Many accidents can be avoided, which lowers the number of disabilities. With fewer people with disabilities in our society, social stigmatization and discrimination will be proportionately less of a problem for society and employers. Employers can perform simpler jobs without coming out as prejudiced against PWD or anti-disables. In order to accommodate people with impairments, businesses do not necessarily need to make costly adjustments to their workplace. According to the employment organization, 80% of people with impairments don't need any changes to be accommodated at work. Where modifications are necessary, the average price would only be £80 (\$167). The prevention of diseases that cause impairment hinders development. The prevalence of health issues that result in disability can be considerably decreased by focusing on environmental factors such as diet, avoidable diseases, clean water and sanitation, safety on the roads and in the workplace. The advantages and significance of hiring people with disabilities are cited in this paper. However, it does not explicitly address the costs versus benefits of hiring people with impairments. However, it is undeniably true that every society can advance to a better and higher socioeconomic status by embracing and utilizing the potential of every member.

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²⁸ *The UK's economy would rise by 13 billion dollars (\$27.1 billion) for six months.*

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